

A Research on “The Paradigm Shifts of Marketing from 1.0 to 5.0”: With Special Reference to Marketing shifts in the FMCG sector

Aqsa Khalid

Assistant Professor, Department of Training & Placement, KIMS, Affiliated to AKTU Lucknow, U.P., India

Corresponding Author Email: aqsakhalid999@gmail.com

Abstract— "Marketing management is the art and science of choosing target markets and getting, keeping and growing customers through creating, delivering and communicating superior customer values of management." Marketing involves the creation and satisfaction of needs and desires. With the recent lifestyle change, the consumer's buying behavior also varies. Such variations bring shifts in the marketing paradigms to enhance the effectiveness of the product and its reach. From being commodity focused to Institutional focused to Functional focused to Managerial focused to finally being Socially focused, Marketing goes through a paradigm shift **Objective:** The study aims to analyze the shifts in marketing in the field of Fast Moving Consumer Goods. There are many significant changes in the strategies for marketing, Fast Moving Consumer Goods in such a manner that helps the GDP growth besides the brand's growth. From being product oriented to being technological and socially responsible, the brands change their strategies to promote and sell themselves along with CSR activities. **Research Methodology:** The research is entirely based on secondary data and is exploratory. The method used to find out acceptable research gaps is Content Analysis. **Practical Implementation:** The study's findings will help marketers understand the shifts in marketing and identify the current trends that promote brands positively and effectively. It also clarifies the impact of CSR activities on the brand image.

Keywords: Paradigm shift, CSR, GDP, Technology growth.

I. INTRODUCTION

II BACKGROUND FOR RESEARCH

Philip Kotler states, "Marketing is the science and art of exploring, creating, and delivering value to satisfy the needs of a target market at a profit." Marketing is vast and pervasive. The shifts in marketing bring variation in the approach and strategies. From being subjected to the Traditional four Ps, marketing revolves around the production and the product. By the end of the 20th century, product-oriented marketing brought space for Customer centered strategies. While keeping the same pace, value-centered marketing becomes Digital oriented marketing to finally pass through marketing focused on Technology for humanity and social responsibility.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.I MARKETING 1.0

Marketing 1.0 is the traditional marketing approach where things focus on production, not the product or the consumer but the production. Marketing doesn't stand still; it is constantly changing and adapting to the environment. Marketing in its 1.0 era was considered as only selling and using tools to generate demand.

According to the findings of 'The Evolution of Marketing 1.0 to Marketing 5.0' by Sanya Mahta, "Marketing 1.0 was a concept that first emerged in the 1930s. Marketing 1.0, the first stage of marketing, consists of several models: production, product, selling, and marketing (Alin, L., 2019). The main objective of this stage was to sell products (Kotler P., 2010). It is the most basic, fundamental phase of marketing, where the main focus relies on the product and its features. The Industrial Revolution proved the perfect catalyst for the expansion of Marketing 1.0 (Jara A., 2012). It provided a situation where there was a boom in the needs of the consumers, and thus there was a drastic increase in both the demand for the products and the competition among the businesses. This provided a need for Marketing. The Marketing focused on the Unique Selling Proposition to distinguish one product from its competitors. They focused on the functional aspect of the products to sell the products to customers, as their core focus was to address the customers' immediate needs without considering the aesthetic value."

II.II MARKETING 2.0 (CUSTOMER-ORIENTED ERA)

Marketing 1.0 was the kind of marketing that was intrusive, interruptive, and one-style for all. Marketing 2.0 is more about conversation, collaboration, and word of mouth. New Marketing 2.0 strategies have great potential to create new achievements through messaging alignment; building shared purpose and vision; marketing governance aimed at helping the organization live the brand; and education and socialization to achieve buy-in for new marketing initiatives.

According to Abdulrahman Aldhaheri and Christian Bach, "To survive in today's market environment, it has become essential for marketers to reorganize their businesses and make good use of the Web 2.0 technology and social media. The merge between Web 2.0 technology and marketing practice would result in adopting what is known as marketing 2.0".

Marketing 2.0 As **Kotler** explains in the interview above, "Some companies decide to learn more about to whom they are selling their products, set out to fabricate and sell quality goods, to understand their clients through the study of large databases and to offer them a differential service."

Marketing 2.0 focuses on *the Customer to establish an emotional bond between him and the product or service*. The second era of Marketing is based on social networking sites in which the consumer is the focal point for the company. It refers to *the new generation of marketing ideas emerging from the Internet era*. The expression became famous in 2005, along with the concept of Web 2.0. It is a buzzword for.ms part of the business jargon of corporate work environments about new marketing means.

II.III MARKETING 3.0 (VALUES-DRIVEN ERA)

In recent years, marketing moved from being product oriented to consumer-oriented. Philip Kotler says, "Marketing 3.0 lifts the marketing concept into the arena of human aspirations, values, and spirit. Marketing 3.0 believes consumers are complete human beings whose other needs and hopes should never be neglected. Therefore, Marketing 3.0 complements emotional marketing with human spirit marketing."

The era of Marketing 3.0 is where variations influence marketing practices in consumer behavior and attitude. It is the much more lined and sophisticated form of the consumer-centric generation in which the demands of consumer\customer are more collaborative, cultural, and spiritual marketing approaches.

Marketing 3.0 clearly defines and strengthens *your unique identity with authentic integrity to build a strong image*. After this, Marketing should no longer be considered as only selling and using tools to generate demand. Marketing should now be regarded as the central hope of a company to restore consumer trust and retain customer loyalty.

When a brand communicates its mission to the consumer comprehensively, it becomes its brand. In this age of growing social media, it is feasible, easy, and convenient for people to talk about different brands, products, services, and their image regarding functional and social performance. Companies must reinvent themselves to shift the safe-zoned strategies and replace them with Marketing 3.0.

II.IV. MARKETING 4.0 (TRADITIONAL TO DIGITAL)

In Marketing 3.0, we talked about the significant shift from product-driven marketing (1.0) to customer-centric marketing (2.0) and ultimately to human-centric marketing (3.0). In Marketing 3.0, we observed customers transforming into whole human beings with minds, hearts, and spirits.

According to Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital, "Marketing 4.0 is a marketing approach that combines online and offline interaction between companies and customers". Kotler also says that marketing will continue to exist as people know it, but digital will keep gaining more and more strength, becoming the main reason for brands' results. This is due to the internet's and social networks' growth and power. Both can influence individuals. In this digitized economy, more than the digital interaction of brands is required. In fact, in this increasingly online, fast-paced world, offline touch signifies a strong differentiation Marketing 4.0 also blends style with substance. Finally, Marketing 4.0 leverages machine-to-machine connectivity to improve marketing productivity while boosting human-to-human connectivity for increased customer engagement.

But in the same vein, Marketing 4.0 also acknowledges that customers still appreciate a balance of offline interaction with brands and companies. It emphasizes the need for marketing initiatives by companies to span a plethora of mediums of communication — multi or omnichannel, if you will — to engage with customers. It's all about connectivity through various mediums.

The traditional Marketing mix (the four P's) should be redefined as the four C's (co-creation, currency, communal activation, and conversation). The essence of Marketing 4.0 is to identify the shifting roles of traditional and digital marketing in forming strong engagement of consumers along with their loyalty. *Marketing 4.0 shows marketers need to balance Technology's immense power with a genuine effort for a "human touch" while being socially responsible*.

Marketing 4.0 is a marketing approach that *integrates the online aspect of interaction with offline interaction* to get the best of both worlds. It helps marketers transition to the digital economy, which has redefined critical marketing concepts. Digital and traditional marketing coexist in Marketing 4.0 to win customer trust and advocacy.

II.V. MARKETING 5.0 (DIGITAL AND SOCIALLY FOCUSED MARKETING)

Marketing 5.0 is the integration of human-centric marketing 3.0 with technology-driven Marketing 4.0. It materializes against three significant challenges: the generation gap, prosperity polarization, and the digital divide.

Marketing 5.0, by definition, is the application of human-mimicking technologies to create, communicate, deliver, and enhance value across the customer journey. One of the critical themes in Marketing 5.0 is the next tech, a group of technologies that aim to emulate the capabilities of human marketers. It includes AI, sensors, robotics, augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), IoT, and blockchain. A combination of these technologies is the enabler of Marketing 5.0.

In the below diagram, it shows "How Humans Add Value to Tech-Driven Marketing":

The authors of Marketing 5.0 do not solely focus on growth, ROI, and 'next tech.' They are also concerned with the polarization of society. That is aggressive growth over decades leading to environmental impact and rising inequality. In summary, companies cannot thrive and survive if they ignore the external consequences of their actions.

Additionally, they argue that businesses must invest "back into society with purpose". Various neglected segments reduce the market size available to companies so social activism can sustainably stimulate markets to grow in the long term. Next, tech helps accelerate progress and create new opportunities.

To sum up all:

- **Marketing 1.0** — a practice that is **focused on products**. The main idea is to highlight the features and benefits of the product and convince a potential consumer to make a purchase decision;
- **Marketing 2.0** — a **customer-oriented approach**. This stage of marketing evolution is closer to what we perceive as marketing today since it shifts the focus to customer needs;
- **Marketing 3.0** — a **human-centric marketing approach**. Although it may resemble the previous stage, there's a significant difference. This stage is more about transforming a company to reflect human values;
- **Marketing 4.0** — the **transition from traditional to digital marketing techniques**. Brands become closer to their consumers while technologies bring about changes in power dynamics and a new type of Customer.
- **Marketing 5.0**— **Marketing 5.0 integrates human-centric marketing 3.0 with technology-driven Marketing 4.0. The application of human-mimicking technologies to create, communicate, deliver, and enhance value across the customer journey.**

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

III.I. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The following are the objectives of this research:

- The research aims to outline the significant shifts in marketing orientation.
- The study is focused on bringing out the prominent CSR activist's brand, the brand which contributes more to GDP, a brand that is a consumer brand, and which brand is more technologically advanced.
- The aim is to mark off the paradigm shifts in the implementation of marketing from the Production concept to the Technology + Social concept.

- The intent is to highlight which firms emphasize more Technology, which is working for Technology along with being socially responsible.
- The focus is to analyze reports of 4 firms in the FMCG sector and get an overview of whose approach is better than the other. HUL, Nestle, ITC FMCG, and Dabur India Ltd. are the companies studied in the research.
- The objective is to find how firms and products contribute to humanity while promoting Technology as a medium.

III.II. RESEARCH TYPE

The research is entirely based on secondary data and is exploratory. The method used to find out acceptable research gaps is Content Analysis. In this paper, frequency analysis is implemented, focusing on explicit data. The study's content analysis method is Word Frequency count to understand the outcomes comprehensively. The firms analyzed in this study are:

- Dabur India Ltd.
- ITC FMCG
- Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL)
- Nestle

The years considered to outline the shifts are 2018,2019,2020,2021, and 2022.

IV. CONTENT ANALYSIS AND DATA INTERPRETATION

The Analysis is done using Word Count Frequency with the help of defined keywords. The Thematic Analysis summarizes the content analysis of all the materials considered. The study includes Reports for the Years 2018,2019,2020,2021 and 2022. The summarized Keywords base used for Analysis is below:

- CSR
- GDP
- Responsibility
- Digital
- Technology
- Social
- Society
- Welfare
- We

Word frequency of predefined keywords is interpreted in the form of bar charts. The reports are summarized comprehensively to stretch out the lining of firms and their marketing strategies while analyzing their role in the welfare of society.

The charts below summarize data collected after analyzing the Annual reports of Dabur, Nestle, HUL, and ITC FMCG each year from 2018 to 2022. These charts show the use and inclusion of keywords in the working approach of the considered firms.

→ **Dabur India Ltd.**

- As for Dabur India Ltd, from Graph 1, the words 'CSR,' 'GDP,' and 'We' have been increasingly mentioned over the last five years. Because of the Pandemic, the 2019 and 2022 eras saw a significant expansion of digital mediums and technology growth. Social responsibility, sustainability, and the welfare of society are also taught in marketing strategies.
- Dabur Chawanprash, Real Juice, Hajmola, and Amla Hair Oil are some mainstream products of Dabur FMCG.
- Dabur India also started a lot of campaigns where they outshine themselves as a socially active and sustainable outreach brand.
- Dabur used Technology as a medium to promote the products and build a brand image satisfactorily strategized as 5.0's methods.
- The Digital Campaigns have been in speedy action ever since COVID-19. The marketing of products and brand building has been integrated with Technology and tradition at the core. In Annual Reports 2019-20 under "Enhancing Consumer Experience," Dabur implemented many Campaigns that are still going with the same dynamism.

→ **Nestle India Limited**

- Nestle India Ltd. is one of the most socially aware brands of the FMCG sector, offering many mainstream products like Nescafé, KitKat, Nespresso, and Maggi, along with more than 2,000 brands and provides a variety of goods in several markets, such as coffee, water bottles, milkshakes and other refreshments, snack foods, baby foods, achievement and healthcare nutrition, seasonings, soups and sauces, frozen and refrigerated foods, and pet food.
- The 2018 Reports outline that the CSR, Technology, and digital aspects were just introductory to the firm. Still, by the end 2019, the firm's strategies were more socially operative than any brand.
- From the graph, we can trace the appearance of the keywords in the annual reports each year, and from that, we can find the scale of technological growth and how the firm is socially responsible towards society and its welfare.
- At the end of 2019 and the beginning of 2020, Nestle started a campaign for Malnourished children, Project HILLDAARI (Plastic Waste Management Awareness Campaign), Project Vriddhi (Rural Development), and others for social welfare.

→ **Hindustan Unilever Limited**

- Hindustan Unilever Limited is a significant name in the field of FMCG. The brand holds leading household brands such as Lux, Lifebuoy, Surf Excel, Rin, Wheel, Glow & Lovely, Pond's, Vaseline, Lakmé, Dove, Clinic Plus, Sunsilk, Pepsodent, Closeup, Axe, Brooke Bond, Bru, Knorr, Kissan, Kwality Wall's, Horlicks and Pureit.
- HUL stretches the marketing strategies that help the brand to incorporate the identity and image of the brand. HUL came across as a large FMCG brand that captures every country household. This advantage allows HUL to build many awareness programs under CSR.
- The year 2019 to the year 2022, the graph predicts the emerging concepts of digitalization and growth in the organization. HUL actively takes initiatives using traditional, digital mediums, or both to capture market share. The contribution to the GDP and implementation of new practices in marketing is positively included more after each previous year.
- HUL is a significant role player in the FMCG sector. With its creative placement and USP, it is a brand that every household has. The company implements its CSR initiatives through Hindustan Unilever Foundation (HUF). HUF operates the 'Water for Public Good' program, Swachh Aadat Swachh Bharat, Asha Daan, Project Sanjeevani, etc.
- "The Bin Boy" is a new campaign advertisement for Waste Management under the CSR activities of HUL.

→ ITC FMCG

- ITC's world-class FMCG brands, including Aashirvaad, Sunfeast, Yippee!, Bingo!, B Natural, ITC Master Chef, Fabelle, Sunbean, Fiamma, Engage, Vivel, Savlon, Classmate, Paperkraft, Mangaldeep, Aim, etc.
- From 2018 to 2022, one can conclude from the graph that ITC emphasized CSR activities and their implementation. The digital growth of the brand also expanded positively.
- The e-choupal portal is ITC's largest platform for agriculture and farmers. The platform is technologically ahead of its time, the same as the vision of ITC.
- The digital medium for brand placement and human interaction with brands has elevated over the years.
- The Brands undertake social welfare and social responsibility more positively. The strategies which are beneficial to society are actively promoted.
- ITC is a huge company and, working across different sectors of business, is actively engaged in CSR activities having the vision to serve a larger National Purpose of Nation building through core values so that every part of society has the chance and the accessibility to the basic needs which rural India doesn't have through imparting assistance and education to uplift them from poverty and misery these people have been facing from a very long time.

V. RESULTS

DABUR:

Dabur India Ltd. is leading in CSR activities among the researched brands. Dabur is implementing marketing with the help of socially responsible instinct and creating the stimulus of awareness among the consumer of the products. From the annual report 2019-20, it can be seen that Dabur India implemented more than ten programs under CSR, such as Immune India, Water, Sanitation & Hygiene (WASH), Swasthya Aur Suraksha, COVID Support Initiatives, Health Camps, Environment Sustainability Project, etc. The conclusion can be drawn after analyzing the "Social Capital" section of the Dabur India Annual Report 2019-20.

"Today, our spends on Digital platforms, including e-commerce, account for around 20% of the total Advertising spends, up from 12.7% a year ago. 130 Digital First/Digital Only films were created and aired across platforms in the 2020-21 financial year. In addition, 830 videos were created on YouTube linked to Health, Lifestyle, and Beauty." - Report 2020-21.

The above paragraphs give an outline of the emerging e-commerce and technology growth of Dabur. The technical and social development of Dabur is still positive. The brand is creating social awareness regarding major topics using different internet

mediums. The firm claims to produce organic and sustainable products to this date to help society be a better place for future generations. The advertisement approach is more socially and consumer-centered, and one can easily find themselves attracted to the product because of the appealing approach of advertisement, choice of product placement, endorsement, and pricing of the products while keeping the economic premise of the target groups.

NESTLE:

Nestle India Ltd. is implementing consumer-centered marketing strategies along with the act of social welfare. The major products under the brand conclave sensitive topics of society by building a meaningful impact. The Marketing and placement of Maggie as Nation's Noodle, but the advertisement focusing on the bond of mother and son, shows the emotional aspect of the consumer of the product. Nestle markets its development as an emotional stigma in the brain of its consumers.

Nestle is majorly known for Maggie's range of noodles, sauces, masala and Kit-Kat, Bar One, Milky Bar, Cereals Range, Nestle baby food range, and dairy range, including Milkmaid, cream, and Renowned coffee range. After the Pandemic, Nestle introduced many Plant-based products for Vegan Consumers. Nestle may not be better than Dabur in CSR activities, but the product game of Nestle is quite strong. The R&D team of Nestle holds the brand up as the other competitors create a new buzz with their products. Nestle is advanced in the technological aspect and the digital usage of the mediums to promote the brands as per the usage of the target audience medium and contribute to the economy's growth. The brand creates buzz with its unique advertisement style and product placement. Nestle India has taken extraordinary and innovative CSR initiatives to work shoulder-to-shoulder with the Indian Government to bolster the economy and well-being of Indians, from cleanliness drives to water conservation programs to Nutrition help programs.

HUL:

HUL is a significant role player in the FMCG sector. The 'Marketing Strategy of HUL' Article from Knowitall concluded, "The company has been able to grow its market share in the category even as other players have been struggling.

It is attributed to the company's ability to keep up with consumer trends and adapt its marketing strategies accordingly. Hindustan Unilever has created a unique brand identity by focusing on consumer trends. With this, they have also managed to get their products into the homes of people not traditionally considered their target market."

With its creative placement and USP, it is a brand that every household has. The company implements its CSR initiatives through Hindustan Unilever Foundation (HUF). HUF operates the 'Water for Public Good' program, Swachh Aaad Swachh Bharat, Asha Daan, Project Sanjeevani, etc. The Bin Boy" is a new campaign advertisement for the CSR activities of HUL. HUL is a blend of both good-selling products and a socially responsible brand.

ITC:

Per the summarization of annual reports, ITC is more technologically advanced than many other brands in its sector. ITC offers satisfaction to consumers of diverse needs with its vast and versatile range of products. The company emerges as one of the biggest names in the country, doing business in different sectors along with FMCG, hotels and restaurants, information and Technology, agri-business, etc.

The trump card for ITC is the ITC's E-Choupal initiative designed to make the Internet accessible to Indian farmers in the rural part of the country. With the help of this initiative, ITC expands its reach to places with low internet connectivity. ITC is establishing itself as a big name in the digital marketing field.

Also, ITC spends more on CSR than other leading names like HUL. The projects include agriculture, health and hygiene, education, skill development, and rural development for the betterment and welfare of society. In comparing its five-year data, ITC indeed rises as a technically advanced brand that is socially responsible towards the interest and knows how to capture the market by severe segmentation.

VI. CONCLUSION

- The research paper is focused on studying shifts in marketing concerning the FMCG sector. The paper considers significant names of the industry and analyzes them.
- The four studied firms are entirely different from each other, having varying competitive advantages towards each other.
- The research paper briefly studies the implications of Technology, CSR activities, and the advancement and growth of both the firm and society. There is still scope to explore the variables about the advertisement style, placement, and pricing of the products as consumer interaction affects their demands.
- ITC is technologically more advanced and uses that as its strength to gain more and more consumers to its name.

- HUL has a diverse product range that helps HUL to be a part of every Indian Household, and this strength of HUL allows the products to contribute to GDP growth and Social Welfare.
- Dabur is an organic and Ayurvedic brand from the customers' perspective. Dabur is one of the most socially active brands of the century.
- Nestle offers every age group a brand of their own. From baby food to coffee to Vegan and Plant-based products, Nestle builds a cage that keeps the consumer within its thresholds.
- Each brand is positively working for the welfare of society late or early. Dabur, an early bird, implemented more projects for the CSR and growth of the organization. Nestle contributed much of its profit to help malnourished children with waste management activities and other general awareness projects. ITC uses its technological advancement as a medium to reach out to people who don't know about the brand. ITC is building a name in the digital marketing application field. HUL contributed more to CSR than the mentioned three firms, contributing to ad campaigns for awareness programs and building products that will reach houses of the nation; HUL is a brand of the country.
- The study still needs to bring in-depth the strategies these firms implied and how they will uphold themselves in the era where Marketing 6.0 is just a knock away.
- The study has a scope of more elaborated research of the firms and their essential products in the market, helping the brands keep their identity as strong as always.

REFERENCES

Websites:

1. <https://www.marketing-psycho.com/marketing-3-0/>
2. <https://for-managers.com/marketing-4-0/>
3. <https://www.adcore.com/blog/what-is-marketing-4-0-how-to-use-it-to-reach-the-consumer-4-0/>
4. <https://bschool.dpu.edu.in/Blogs/marketing-5-0-technology-for-humanity/>
5. <https://rioks.com/blog/marketing-5-0-the-future-of-marketing/>
6. <https://www.think-beyond.co.uk/marketing-5-0-and-understanding-modern-marketing-lessons/#:~:text=Marketing%20is,value%20across%20the%20customer%20journey.> by%20
7. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/160499976.pdf>
8. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352900816000029>
9. <https://www.publichealth.columbia.edu/research>
10. <https://gradcoach.com/qualitative-content-analysis/>
11. online marketing Archives - Digital Freshman. <https://digitalfreshman.com/tag/online-marketing/>
12. Hermawan Kartajaya Archives - Marketing Psycho. <https://www.marketing-psycho.com/tag/hermawan-kartajaya/>
13. Marketing 4.0 by Hermawan Kartajaya, Philip Kotler, Iwan Setiawan - Ebook | Scribd. <https://www.scribd.com/book/331610192/Marketing-4-0-Moving-from-Traditional-to-Digital>
14. Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital. – Reputiva. <https://www.reputiva.com/marketing-4-0-moving-from-traditional-to-digital/>
15. Marketing 4.0: All About New Mindsets and New Approaches - For-managers. <https://for-managers.com/marketing-4-0/>
16. Marketing 4.0: All About New Mindsets and New Approaches - For-managers. <https://for-managers.com/marketing-4-0/>
17. “Marketing 5.0: Technology for Humanity” – An Interview with Hermawan Kartajaya and Iwan Setiawan. <https://www.marketingjournal.org/marketing-5-0-technology-for-humanity-an-interview-with-hermawan-kartajaya-and-iwan-setiawan/>
18. Marketing 5.0: The Future of Marketing & Technology. <https://rioks.com/blog/marketing-5-0-the-future-of-marketing/>
19. “Marketing 5.0: Technology for Humanity” – An Interview with Hermawan Kartajaya and Iwan Setiawan. <https://www.marketingjournal.org/marketing-5-0-technology-for-humanity-an-interview-with-hermawan-kartajaya-and-iwan-setiawan/>
20. CSR on ITC Ltd.. <https://pt.slideshare.net/adityachaturvedi980/csr-on-itc-ltd>
21. What is the Ad spend of FMCG Companies? - PA Wealth. <https://blog.pawealth.in/2021/11/23/what-is-the-ad-spend-of-fmcg-companies/>
22. Corporate social responsibility initiatives of Nestle - iLeaders. <https://blog.ipleaders.in/corporate-social-responsibility-initiatives-nestle/>
23. Product mix of hul ~ Products, Consumers - Investor Guruji. <https://investorguruji.com/product-mix-of-hul/>

Dabur:

24. <https://www.dabur.com/investor/financial-information/reports/1289/Annual-Reports>
25. <https://www.dabur.com/amp/in/en-us/investor/financial-information/reports/annual-reports/2021-22>
26. <https://www.dabur.com/amp/in/en-us/investor/financial-information/reports/annual-reports/2020-21>

HUL:

27. <https://www.hul.co.in/files/92ui5egz/production/deffeb1a406d0dda5445caa3d5731b849a137bf1.pdf>
28. <https://www.hul.co.in/files/92ui5egz/production/8a1b3f103408328781a6ebf434b8e5172e4bfc91.pdf>
29. <https://trendlyne-media-mumbai-new.s3.amazonaws.com/uploaded-documents/annual-report/>
30. https://ijariie.com/AdminUploadPdf/Corporate_Social_Responsibility_A_Comparative_Study_of_CSR_Initiatives_of_HUL_and_ITC_Ltd_in_India_ijariie15304.pdf
31. <https://knowitall.in/marketing-strategy-of-hul/>

ITC:

32. <https://www.itcportal.com/about-itc/shareholder-value/annual-reports/itc-annual-report-2018/pdf/ITC-Report-and-Accounts-2018.pdf>
33. <https://www.itcportal.com/about-itc/shareholder-value/annual-reports/itc-annual-report-2019/pdf/ITC-Report-and-Accounts-2019.pdf>
34. <https://www.itcportal.com/about-itc/shareholder-value/annual-reports/itc-annual-report-2020/pdf/ITC-Report-and-Accounts-2020.pdf>
35. <https://www.itcportal.com/about-itc/shareholder-value/annual-reports/itc-annual-report-2021/pdf/ITC-Report-and-Accounts-2021.pdf>
36. <https://www.itcportal.com/about-itc/shareholder-value/annual-reports/itc-annual-report-2022/pdf/ITC-Report-and-Accounts-2022.pdf>

Nestle:

37. <https://www.nestle.in/investors/stockandfinancials/annualreports>
38. https://www.nestle.in/sites/g/files/pydnoa451/files/investors/stockandfinancials/documents/annual_report/nestle-india-annual-report-final-2018.pdf
39. <https://www.nestle.in/sites/g/files/pydnoa451/files/2020-05/Nestle-India-Annual-Report-2019.pdf>
40. <https://www.nestle.in/sites/g/files/pydnoa451/files/2022-03/Nestle-India-AGM-Notice-and-Annual-Reports-Signed.pdf>
41. <https://blog.ipleaders.in/corporate-social-responsibility-initiatives-nestle/>

Books:

42. "Marketing 2.0: Bridging the gap between Seller and Buyer through Social Media Marketing" by Bernie Borges.
43. "Marketing 3.0: From Products to Customers to the Human Spirit" by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya, and Iwan Setiawan.
44. "Marketing 4.0: Moving from Traditional to Digital" by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya, and Iwan Setiawan.
45. "Marketing 5.0: Technology for Humanity" by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya and Iwan Setiawan.
46. "Marketing management" by Arun Kumar -N.Meenakshi
47. "Marketing Management" by Rajan Saxena
48. "Principles of Marketing Management" by Kotler Philip 12th Edition Prentice-Hall of India

Paper:

49. *Corporate Social Responsibility- A Comparative Study of CSR Initiatives of HUL and ITC Ltd. in India:* Dr. Praveen B. Patil, Prof. Pavankumar C. Ramgouda. Jain College of MCA and MBA, Belagavi (Vol-7 Issue-5 2021) IJARIII- ISSN(O)-2395-4396
50. "An overview of content analysis" *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation:* Steve Stemler, (2001- Vol. 7, Article 17)

51. **Word Power: A New Approach for Content Analysis:** Narasimhan Jegadeesh, Di Wu (July 2013)
52. **Qualitative Analysis of Content:** Yan Zhang and Barbara M. Wildemuth
53. **Marketing strategies for fast-moving consumer goods:** Jan-Benedict E.M. Steenkamp & Marnik G. Dekimpe (Nov 2009)
54. **Marketing Strategy on different stages PLC and its marketing implications on FMCG products:** Dr. Neetu Sharma (Vol.2, No. 3, March 2013)
55. **'Marketing strategy of FMCG product' A case study of Hindustan Unilever Limited:** Dr. Suganthi V (Volume 1; Issue 9; September 2016)
56. **'OOH' Morphs to "DOOH": AdOnMo Sets Advertising from Motionless to Motion.** Gupta, D., Biswas, A., Sukhwai, A., & Karnai, M. (2022). South Asian Journal of Management, 29(1), 149.
57. **Effective marketing strategies for global FMCG brands during COVID-19 pandemic crisis:** Meletios I. Niros, [Angelica Niros](#), [Yannis Pollalis](#), [Qing Shan Ding](#) (August 2022)
58. **Marketing Mix Strategies for FMCG Companies in India:** Dr. Sharma Sanjay, Dr. Sharma Priyanka (Year: 2017, Volume: 8, Issue: 4)
59. **Customer Perception on Marketing Mix Adopted By ITC and HUL:** Dr.Sanjay Sharma Assistant Professor, Dr. V.K. Gautam, Dr.Priyanka Sharma (Vol.7 Issue 7, July 2017)
60. **Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Fmcg Products with Reference to Toilet Soap:** Dr. Jena Artta Bandhu, Mr. Panda Snehasis (Year: 2018, Volume: 7, Issue: 5)
61. **The Evolution of Marketing 1.0 to Marketing 5.0:** Sanya Mehta (Volume 5, Issue 4)